
THINKING OF ISLAMIC EDUCATION IN THE GOLDEN TIME OF ISLAM

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Abstract

Islamic history records that the Abbasid period was the "golden age" of Islam, especially during the reign of Harun al-Rashid and al-Makmum, because of the intellectual sciences such as philosophy, geometry, mathematics, astronomy, chemistry, history, and geography. At this time has begun to enter and emerge, the development of educational institutions, as well as the birth of great educational ideas. It is not surprising that at this time there were prominent ulama (imam) such as Imam Abu Hanifah (80-150 H), Imam Malik (95-179 H), Imam Shafi'i (150-204), Imam Ahmad bin Hambal (164-241 H). H), known as Aimmatu mazahib al-Arba'ah (four priests of the fiqh school) which is still followed by Muslims around the world.

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A. Introduction

The golden age of Islam was achieved during the reign of the Abbasid Sovereign from 750-1258 AD (Thohir, 2004: 53). At this time, Islam was progressing in the fields of Economics, Science, Technology, Philosophy, and especially education. The education system in the era of Islamic glory has been able to awaken all lines of people's lives. Education and science received great attention by the holders of the power of the Abbasid Sovereign.

The Abbasid sovereign was very prominent in the field of education, especially during the reign of Caliph Harun al-Rashid and al-Makmum. The two Caliphs were famous for being very intelligent and very fond of science and scientists. Science has developed very rapidly and made this Islamic Sovereign the most advanced country in the field of education and science in the world at that time.

During the heyday of Islam, many Islamic scientists and thinkers were born, such as al-Ghazali, al-Kindi, Ibn Sina, and others. Similarly, educational and scientific institutions emerged, such as Bait al-Hikmah, Nizhamiyah University, al-Mustanshiriyah University (Baghdad), al-Azhar University (Cairo), and others (Amin, 2004:253-259).

However, the thoughts relating to the education of these figures did not receive the attention of Muslim scholars, especially Western scholars (orientalists), even though the bright ideas of Muslim thinkers in the golden age of Islam were proven to have been able to lead Muslims towards peak of success at that time. Even in the West at that time, many studied with them (Islamic thinkers) and adopted their ideas, so that the West could eventually outperform Muslims in the fields of science and technology, especially education.

B. Theoretical Review

1. Understanding Islamic Education Thought

Etymologically, thinking comes from the root word "think" (from Arabic), which means the process, method, or activity of thinking, which is using the mind to decide a problem by considering everything wisely. In other words, thinking is an intelligent effort from the working process of the mind and heart to see symptoms and try to find solutions wisely (A. Susanto, 2009: 2-3)

While education is a process of preparing the younger generation to run life and fulfill their life goals more effectively and efficiently (Azra, 2002: 3). Education is not only a transfer of knowledge, but also a transformation of values and character building with all its aspects. While teaching is the process of transferring knowledge from a teacher (teacher) to the person being taught (students, students, students).

Education is the process of forming individuals based on Islamic teachings to achieve high degrees so that they are able to carry out their duties to their caliphate and succeed in realizing happiness in the world and the hereafter (Nata, 2010: 10). So Islamic education is wider in scope and has a higher purpose because it not only produces people who are knowledgeable and capable of carrying out leadership tasks in the world, but also creates people who are happy servants of God (the hereafter).

Islamic education is different from secular (Western) education which only forms human beings who are smart in their fields (specialists) and focuses on achieving mere physical or material happiness and does not care about the moral aspect, so that the products are intellectual but immoral and morally human beings. It is easy for them to use their knowledge for the sake of individual interests, not for the benefit of the people. Islamic education is more directing humans to achieve happiness in the world and the hereafter in a balanced way, knowing how to have good morals towards Allah as the Creator, towards fellow humans and other creatures of God.

In terminology, Islamic education thinking is a series of mind and heart work processes that are carried out seriously in looking at the various problems that exist in Islamic education and trying to build an educational paradigm that is able to become a vehicle for the complete coaching and development of students (A. Susanto, 2009). : 3-4). So, through this approach, it is hoped that Islamic education will be able to lead students to become fully human, not only intelligent and knowledgeable, but also have good morals.

2. Thoughts on Islamic Education in the Golden Age of Islam

Islamic history records that the Abbasid period was the "golden age" of Islam, especially during the reign of Harun al-Rashid and al-Makmum, because of the intellectual sciences such as philosophy, geometry, mathematics, astronomy, chemistry, history, and geography. At this time has begun to enter and emerge, the development of educational institutions, as well as the birth of great educational ideas. It is not surprising that at this time there were prominent ulama (imam) such as Imam Abu Hanifah (80-150 H), Imam Malik (95-179 H), Imam Shafi'i (150-204), Imam Ahmad bin Hambal (164-241 H). H), known as *Aimmatu mazahib al-Arba'ah* (four priests of the fiqh school) which is still followed by Muslims around the world. In addition, the famous Imam al-Muhadditsin also appeared, namely Imam al-Bukhari (A. Susanto, 2009: 29).

During the reign of Harun al-Rashid and continued by al-Makmum, there was a massive translation movement of Greek, Persian, and Indian science and philosophy into Arabic. As a result, some of the Muslim scholars were influenced by foreign knowledge, especially Greek science and philosophy. The works of Greek philosophers such as Plato and Aristotle are considered as very important as the Qur'an. In connection with this, Muslim intellectuals began to interpret Islamic teachings within the framework of Aristotle's thought and sought to harmonize Islamic teachings with Greek philosophy. Of course, this further gave rise to many philosophical doctrines that contradict each other as the *Mu'tazilah* demonstrated (Alavi, 2003: 4). The Abbasid rulers who supported the *Mu'tazilah madhhab*, especially al-Makmum, forced this understanding by force and did not hesitate to kill and imprison the ulama' who did not want to follow their madhhab.

During the Abbasid period, training was held for previously unknown madrasas. The person who first founded the madrasa was Prime Minister Nizham al-Mulk. The coaching of these madrasas shows the peak of Islamic school education (A. Susanto, 2009: 30).

The most important feature of this golden age of Islam is the emergence of Islamic educational thoughts. Muslim scholars at this time competed to write books on education and teaching in a broad and deep manner which indicated a special attention in the field of education. Ibn Sahnun (3rd century H), was the first person to write a book on education, followed by al-Qabisi (4th century H), Ibn Maskawaih and al-Ghazali (6th century H), Ibn Khaldun (4th century H), -8 H). During this period, the author of a book on education named Burhanuddin al-Zarnuji appeared with his

monumental work *Ta'lim al-Muta'allim* (A. Susanto, 2009: 30), which until now is still taught in Islamic boarding schools or schools. *salaf* and become the main reference in teaching ethics and correct learning procedures in the Islamic world.

3. The Purpose of Islamic Education Thought

In particular, the thought of Islamic education has a very important goal. The complex of which is

1. To build habits of scientific, dynamic and critical thinking on issues surrounding Islamic educators.
2. To provide a basis for inclusive thinking towards Islamic teachings and accommodating the development of knowledge developed by intellectuals outside Islam.
3. To foster the spirit of *ijtihad*, as intended by the Prophet and Muslim intellectuals in the first century to the Middle Ages, especially in reconstructing a better Islamic education system.
4. To contribute ideas to the development of the national education system.

C. Conclusion

1. The thought of Islamic education is a series of processes of working the mind and heart seriously in looking at the various problems that exist in Islamic education
2. The purpose of studying Islamic educational thought is to uncover and formulate the paradigm of Islamic education and its role in developing Islamic education
3. During the Abbasid era, Islamic education reached its peak of glory.

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